

SELECTIVE LASER ETCHING: AN ENABLING TECHNOLOGY FOR BOOSTING QUANTUM COMPUTING?

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ABSTRACT

The potential positive impact of quantum computing in several industrial sectors has raised a worldwide effort for the development of a practical quantum computer. In this paper we review on the current key technologies promising to impact the realization of a trapped-ion quantum computer. We focus our discussion on a 3D glass printing technique – selective laser-induced etching (SLE). This technology will facilitate the integration of optical and electronic components and will ultimately be a booster to reach the next level of technological readiness required to implement proof of concept applications.

KEYWORDS: Quantum Computing, Trapped-ion Technology, Microfabrication, Integrated Electronic and Photonic Components, Quantum Technology, Enabling Technologies, 3D glass printing.

INTRODUCTION

Quantum computing has recently gained broad awareness due to its potential capabilities for solving some of the most challenging problems of our time. The positive progress of the development of a practical quantum computer will directly benefit multiple – if not all – industrial sectors. Depending on the maturity of this technology we will witness in the years ahead first applications on optimization-based use cases such as the development of novel materials, the discovery of new drugs, more efficient manufacturing tasks, among others. Although the maturity of quantum computing technology has not yet converged to its ultimate level, there have been significant advances in recent years. Among the most promising quantum computing platforms stand trapped-ion systems.

In this paper, we present an insight into the current manufacturing capabilities for trapped-ion quantum processor chips, as well as into challenges involved in the realization of a practical trapped-ion quantum computer. Trapped ions are one of the most precise and accurate systems that can be used as basis for hosting a quantum unit of information (qubit). In a surface-electrode trap, ions are held by a combination of oscillating (RF) and static (DC) potentials generated by electrodes laying on a common plane. Typically a pair of RF electrodes is required, in a linear or for the case of a scalable QCCD architecture [1] in the form of linear segments interconnected by junctions. The ion transport is provided by the potential generated by a segmented array of DC electrodes. In our approach the quantum control is provided by a magnetic field gradient produced by a module integrated into our ion trap chip. In this scheme, laser beams are only used for preparation, cooling, and detection of the qubit state.

Due to its planar geometry, surface-electrode ion traps are well suited to be manufactured by well-established microfabrication techniques. The material range of choice is typically given by the semiconductor industry standards, where silicon and SOI substrates are extensively used. In silicon-based ion traps, key integrated components such as micro optics [2], on-chip optical waveguides [3], [4] and control electronics [5] have been monolithically fabricated. The on-chip integration efforts have been focused on silicon substrates due to easy machinability and compatibility with standard semiconductor techniques. However, the rf loss properties of Si impose challenges on the design and optimal performance of surface-electrode traps. Ideal dielectric properties of the substrates are often offered by ceramic and glass materials, but their application into the ion trap fabrication workflow is still limited and not yet fully implemented at the industrial level.

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A glass piece can be structured by selective laser-induced etching [6], in which a fs-beam modifies the chemical properties inside the substrate material and makes it prone to etching in an acid or in a strong alkaline solution. A quantum processor will need to include, among other components, several electrical and optical signals.

Currently, electrical signals are brought laterally to the ion trap chip via wirebonding and standard PCB technology. For several hundreds of signals, this leads to blocking of the optical access, thus requiring a vertical integration solution. In the cartoon shown in Fig. 1 it is envisioned that 3D printing manufacturing will enable the necessary vertical interconnection through the chip. On the other hand, the necessary laser beams have been aligned parallel to ion trap chips in most demonstrators to-date. On-chip integration of optical waveguides based on SiN Technology has been demonstrated [3]. The attachment of additional interfaces for light coupling at the edge of chip (not shown in Fig. 1) can certainly be provided by 3D structures realized using the SLE process. 3D features defined on glass have been used for self-alignment of the components of the trap [7], demonstrating the rich possibility of applications when it comes to alignment of ion trap and photonic components.

Applications of the SLE method thus cover a wide range of scenarios from single ion-trap components manufacturing to an entire assembly of a chip system and will positively impact the integration of photonic and electronic components.

Figure 1: Cartoon illustrating a small-scale quantum processor based on the quantum CCD architecture. The orange electrodes provide the necessary RF potential nodal lines above the surface. Small DC electrodes generate slow varying waveforms for ion(s) transport. Laser beams are envisioned to be delivered by on-chip integrated waveguides.

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